

Peace Wall Belfast: Spatial Audio Representation of Divided Spaces and Soundwalks

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ABSTRACT

In West Belfast lays the Peace Wall Belfast, a manifestation of multifaced messages on political, religious, and communal ideals represented by physical properties of cement, metal, fences, gates, and artwork. There have been discussions on initiatives to take down the walls, however, this remains a fragile state. When thinking about the connectivity of the surrounding spaces and communities, the placing of the Peace Wall(s) blocks any opportunity of cross-communication and produces disorienting effects. However, through alternative artistic approaches focusing on sound, there can be innovative capabilities of sharing these stories and spaces with spatial audio techniques. To use spatial audio to change the perception of these spaces brings forth alternative periods of reflections from stimulating another sensory tool other than sight. Forming two unique listening experiences that focus on the virtual abilities to combine auditory spaces into an immersive installation environment and binaural soundwalks to design site-specific augmentation of the sonic properties of the Peace Wall's surrounding spaces. These projects aim at using spatial audio and artistic practice to plan new approaches for conflict transformation in Northern Ireland.

1. INTRODUCTION

Fifty years later, the Falls (Catholic/Nationalist) and Shankill (Protestant/Loyalist) roads in West Belfast remain separated by the placing of a Peace Wall. While there are numerous Peace Walls in the country of Northern Ireland, the Peace Wall Belfast remains popularized with continuous updates of murals, peace messages, and influence with cultural tourism. However, these walls or otherwise known as interfaces, provide local communities a sense of security and comfort. This also hinders the ability to have conversations about the removal of the Peace Walls, territorial resolution, and community transformation. From a visual standpoint, these walls form physical segregation and isolation, as security gates between the walls continue to have regulated schedules of opening and closing.

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The 'Troubles' is a conflict based on the accumulation of a rivaled history with the Loyalists to the United Kingdom and Nationalists desire for a united Ireland. In 1969, it escalated based on ethno-nationalists' movement into politics for a change in civil right movements, to reform political and social areas of life. [1]. Each of the communities began fabricating man-made barriers to form a sense of security from the other. These barriers were then overtaken by the British Army (sought to be a neutral party) to place Peace Walls, for the main purpose of being a temporary measure of protection from each other. [2]. The idea of the Peace Walls was to physically divide either side in attempt at deescalating the violence between the groups, as well as, initiating a mindset of security or protection while political discussions were ongoing. However, this evidently spiraled into chaos and violence between the British Army, local police forces, and paramilitary groups from both communities. During the 29-year conflict, sectarian division was reinforced by the casualties faced from all groups with the addition of innocent bystanders caught in the crossfires, the sense of fear from the other only intensified by this conflict.

Currently, 22 years after the ceasefires that were agreed upon in 1998, these walls are still up and maintained to certain degrees. According to the Belfast Interface Project's [2] study they identified 116 forms of defensive architecture across Northern Ireland, in which 97 are primarily located across the city of Belfast. These forms of defensive structures vary from large-scaled blocks of cement walls to smaller fences, however, any of the identified defensive architectures are deemed as a barrier between communities. By continuing to have the walls within the communities, the struggle to remove them increases, people have become accustomed to the representation of these walls, a sense of psychological and physical security even though no community is fully isolated in the 21st century.

As the city and country move forward with other socio-cultural movements, there is little persuasion in the ideas of permanently removing the Peace Walls. Comparative research studies have been conducted to review attitudes, ideas, perception, and understanding about the Peace Walls to see if change or removal is possible. [2]. Overall, there continues to be mixed results on how people feel about the placement of the walls and the actions of removing them, there is still a strong consensus of keeping them for security from the other community groups presumed violence that may return if they were removed. Since then, Northern Ireland is now faced with the uncertainty brought on from the success of BREXIT,

reoccurring division within Northern Ireland, the impact on relationships between the Republic of Ireland and Europe, and the general balance between all of the UK countries. This now questions the frangibility of discussing unity in any form among any of the areas mentioned above. As a recent example about the country's division, moving away from the Peace Walls, we can examine government leadership in Northern Ireland. It is only recently that agreements have been made when in 2017 the Northern Ireland Assembly or Stormont, which is a consociationalism or "power-sharing" government, collapsed when the British and Irish political groups could not commit to a unified government based on political differences and how to resolve scandal. [3] [4]. This sense of division presides strongly within the country as areas on all scales of politics, economy, history, and social life are separate by one attribute or another. Now more than ever is a time for the country to come together, to listen and find a common solution to move forward.

Delivering messages through art promotes a certain level of engagement and reflection by the audience. It is about the encoded and decoded messages that people seek through art that tempt further discussions. The overall connection to our daily lives and way of thinking. The medium of sound has an important role in localization to spaces. As for most works surrounding the Peace Walls, they have relied on the visual representation whether this be photography, paintings, text, or videography. However, sonic art projects allow to reach new groups of audiences, to increase accessibility and engagement, to change the perspective of a situation, and focus on other sensory information. The more people having access to something creates a possible increase in having a conversation surrounding a topic.

In consideration of the ongoing progression with spatial audio techniques, recording, and software, the capabilities of creating a united space is possible through the fabrication and unification of different audio recordings. This research provides an insight of using spatial audio to create a futuristic understanding of how these spaces may one day unite and react with one another. This is an attempt of using sound to bridge the spaces currently dividing two sets of communities.

The two audio research projects attempt to establish an augmentation of visual spaces through sound with multidisciplinary support of socially engaged arts, urban arts, sonic arts, and physical augmentation sonification. Each project reflects an amount of these disciplines, however, there are also legal constraints that equally changed the project outcomes. For both projects to be successful, there was a maintaining of anonymity and equal neutral representation of both communities.

Approaching these issues through the artistic practices of sonic art provides a platform to embody various sources of academic, artistic, and conflict research to reform perception and engage discussions about conflict transformation. Sound is used as a methodological tool to unite socio-cultural elements between the interactions of people and place. The nature of this research is from a foreign perspective, therefore attempting to establish a neutral viewpoint on these controversial issues. The two projects

will be discussed on sonic material, recording locations, project concepts, project outcomes and the experience of the project demonstrations.

2. SPATIAL AUDIO & SOUNDWALKS

Documenting these site-specific spaces through audio allows for a sense of dual-purpose, to create two uniquely different projects united by history, technology, arts, and sound which circle all around the theme of division and reconciliation. Conventionally, there is division even among science and humanities, the understanding of redistributing information for public understanding. [5]. By embracing ambisonics, technology that records 360-degree audio, it reshapes what can be understood by division, allowing for spaces to be virtually connected. [6]. The technological capabilities of fabricating auditory virtual environments from pieces of different audio material provides the futuristic vision of what a place may sound like if that physical division were removed. Projects such as The Listen(n) Project, an acoustic ecology research based on natural environments in the American Southwest, focus on two mechanisms: sonic properties and sonic activity to retell an environments story. [7]. Ambisonics is one method of preserving auditory spaces, and in terms of Divided Spaces this recreates an entirely new space to be visited and experienced through an installation by reconstructing a large physical space to be accessible in a room listening environment. Additionally, narrative became of importance to guide the listener in both projects, whether that was audio-narration from archival and interviewed people, or through text-narration, reading about the space and history.

In regards with soundwalks and the foundational knowledge established by World Soundscape Project, a listener is intended to sonically absorb on environment, sometimes discover or re-discover sonic elements may have gone unnoticed from the daily life. [8]. However, with these binaural soundwalks, this branches out into another form of the traditional sense of soundwalking, by incorporating technology to enhance the listeners experience and within this project is to amplify events that are either based on periods of time, perception of the other side of the wall, and through sonification – data translated through sound. Paquette and McCartney [9] state that having guided, or predetermined paths may hinder or impose interpretation, even if the soundwalk is meant to raise awareness of those spaces. However, through different soundwalking methods, recording methods, and ethnographic practices, there is an accessibility of numerous forms of information's for the listener to have the freedom of making their own soundwalk experience with the provided materials. Accessible through a website, the combination of documented photos, text, a looped walking path (to find their way around the spaces, not as an audio guide) is intended to be free of such constraints. They may listen to one or all of the binaural recordings, on their own or with a group, with each piece individually crafted for the space.

The use of ambisonics as a primary source of audio material in soundwalks is the ability to capture 360-degree material that can later be reshaped and redistributed into

conventional listening methods through headphones during a soundwalk. This means that through multiple recording sessions, there is an ability to overlay multiple sonic moments into a weaved sonic environment that permits the listener to re-live sonic events from the past as if they were there in that particular moment. This method conflicts with other artists and researchers who conduct soundwalks or soundscapes, some may refrain from technological enhancements, whereas others will implore guidance to direct attention in the space. [10]. However, the soundwalk project is not triggered by GPS location and instead are made flexible to having open interpretations by walking around the space and being loosely informed by the text and photo. This can be seen as either a challenge or opportunity when discussing the authenticity of sonic placement whereas the message of connecting to the space is strengthened.

3. OBJECTIVES

The overall motivation to embark on an artistic research project using spatial audio technologies in concern with the Peace Wall Belfast was because of physical barriers between community spaces and the lack of representation through different senses, particularly sound. According to Obert's [11] experience as a foreigner walking through the spaces around the Peace Wall instils an overall distraught occurrence because of the displacement imposed by the routes around the walls and even the physical dimensions that obstruct visuals. When thinking about sound and the transferable properties over, into, under, and around the walls, there is a capability of capturing another sensory perception from the Peace Wall's manifestation. A sonic art approach allows for individuals to reflect on new forms of engagement and accessibility.

This research involves creative works to produce a focus on the effectiveness of art within the context of conflict transformation. Wallenstein [12] discusses the current management of peace within Northern Ireland which is maintained yet not resolved from outside third-party mediators. While there are also local organizations and community centers who focus on conflict transformation, there is a continuous division represented outside of the city center of Belfast identified with the Peace Walls and security gates. Passing the halfway mark for a 10-year plan to remove the Peace Walls has led to a low percentage of wall removals and there is mixed support from individuals in those communities to keep the structures in place. [13]. The interest to create audio works is to provide new perspectives concerned with a controversial issue that hopes to engage new forms of communication and to reorder the process of information that fixates on the visual stimulus.

4. AUDIO MATERIAL

4.1 Research Methods

Collecting audio material began early October 2018 until late July 2019. During this period there was a combination and experimentation of various recording equipment dependent on variables from the location sites, as well as

interviewed participants. This research was completed with a qualitative field research approach by conducting participant observation (interviews) and direct observation (field recording). Listed below are insights to the challenges and ranges of audio material gathered throughout the year.

4.2 Recording Challenges and Field Locations

Figure 1 - Walking Perimeter in blue

Capturing and representing physical spaces through the medium of sound presents numerous obstacles when conducting field recordings. There is no control over the weather, the amount of traffic, or local noise pollution when recording. This inevitably led to countless efforts of recording on different days, times of the day, and various seasonal periods to gather as much material as possible. As foreign researcher, there is an element of exposure with large eye-catching audio equipment. This initially resulted in using smaller versions of ambisonics recorders Zoom H3-VR however with its low recording capabilities there was a change to using the Sennheiser Ambeo VR Mic which captured the sonic scenery exceptionally well, however this did hinder certain natural human activities.

Choosing locations to record fluctuated between personal comfortability of being exposed in unknown territories and where to receive the most amount of sonic activity to establish an auditory connection or specific sonic markers to those physical spaces. By forming a routine, it would show that my presence was for research and was not to interfere with residents, tourist guides, or tourists. This meant always exposing an identity card from Queen's University Belfast and wearing the same hat no matter the weather. Maintaining this form of distance and appearance aided some parents in the communities to allow their children to approach me near the end of my research. They began to amplify their own presence near the microphones, this also allowed myself to grant them some usage of recording with a contact microphone to gather sounds they found interesting in their community.

The approach through spatial audio allows for an opportunity to capture multiple 360° sonic fields from either side and fabricate two listening experiences. To enhance these audio representations, other recording methods were necessary to aid in the detailing of the auditory scenes, such as stereo recordings (90° capsules with Zoom H6), contact microphones for physical sonification, coil microphones for electromagnetic energy, lapel microphones for interviews, and in-ear binaural microphone/earphones. Gathering various ranges of sounds enables a multi-layered perception of sonic markers and induces auditory imagination from the properties in these spaces.

Collecting audio material for both projects succumbed to the balance of transportability of equipment and quality of microphones. Walking around the Peace Wall in isolated areas with large amounts of equipment was not always ideal since locals or tourists would have negative reactions to certain types of audio equipment exposed. For example, carrying around a hand-held shotgun microphone with a large blimp windscreen scared off many people or they would completely stop moving/chatting if the microphone was within their eyesight. This was in the beginning stages of the research which enforced me to adapt to other modes of recording. Since there was a necessity to use ambisonics microphones, the initial option was to record with the Zoom H3-VR because of its all-in-one compact applications in the field. However, the quality of audio suffered with this method. Ultimately, in the last stages of the research and audio gathering, there was a switch to quality over transportability (using the Sennheiser AMBEO VR Mic with the Zoom F8 MultiTrack Field Recorder) which improved the ability to retain clearer sonic material from the environments.

4.3 BBC Northern Ireland – Archival Material

Audio material from BBC Northern Ireland derives from their personal archives that contains documentaries, news-casts, and other forms of audio-visual sources. To maintain authenticity to the project concept, most of the material used dates between the periods of 1969-1975 and 21st century. Even though some material has blemishes or damages to the audio, it is the messages spoken that are meant to be highlighted. Constrained by legal permissions, the audio selected was only available for Project 1 | Divided Spaces, which also meant producing strict time codes of the original material and position in the project. Therefore, there was not much creative flexibility with the final BBC Northern Ireland materials, and could not repair the audio since that would change the original material granted for this project.

The addition of archival material to the project allows for recollection and year specific information about what was happening to people in Belfast during the ‘Troubles’. This sense of information also allowed to create a starting point for conversation and discussions, to reflect on the mentality of the situation and how we can compare to it 51 years later. Divided Spaces not only attempts at combining the two spaces divided by the wall, it also acts as an auditory timeline of compressed events. Audio-visual material provided by BBC Northern Ireland archivists permits the public to have access to this type of information, granted for the project, that has been stored or forgotten by today’s generation. The best way to gain knowledge is to share knowledge.

The main challenge with this type of material is to remain neutral on such a delegate historic event. With archival material, it is about preservation and sharing that neutrality by removing names, relationships, status, loyalty to a group, and any other indicators that may derail the act of progression. The integrity of the project was to represent equally the story, from different perspectives, but those people documented remain anonymous to the public.

This can be heard in section subtitled Table 1– Sections – Past – 01:32 – 06:17. This challenge also grants an opportunity for people to experience without taking a side to either community. To immerse themselves into the overall story and entice them to research further into the history of the ‘Troubles’.

4.4 Interviews

Interview Questions:

- 1) Are you from Belfast? Which Part?
- 2) Did you live before/through/after The Troubles? How did that affect you?
- 3) What does the Peace Wall mean to you and why?
- 4) What is your earliest memory of the Peace Walls?
- 5) What is one memory of the Peace Wall that you have held onto?
- 6) How does the Peace Wall affect the community?
- 7) Through the perspective of sound, can you define specific sounds that reflect the wall and space?
- 8) If the Peace Wall was taken down, how would the sound of the spaces change?
- 9) Apart from a visual separation, is there any other sense that the wall hinders?
- 10) In one to few words, can you tell me a specific sound that relates with the Peace Wall?

Individuals chosen to take part for the interview portion of the research willingly discussed their relations to the Peace Wall Belfast or general associations with Peace Walls. They were asked questions that formed the narrative for Project 1 | Divided Spaces and also aided me to capture sounds that may represent their experiences through the piece. Due to the mercy of the recording environments and/or persons form of speech, we interviewed whenever/wherever the participant had free time. This means that some recordings are affected by either personal accents or way of speaking and the natural surroundings (traffic noise, wind, building noise, etc...) which all affected the quality of audio. However, this also adds as a distinctive characteristic to the difficulties in gathering information based on the research topic and finding willing participants. Instead of planning and scheduling proper recording sessions, my approach shifted in being a field journalist.

4.5 Ambisonics

Recording ambisonics in two varied sonic environments generated extreme challenges with the amount or lack of amount of sonic activity. When attempting to record on Cupar Way, a highly active road with many tourists, black taxi tour drivers, tourist buses, and local traffic, forced longer recording sessions to then only edit out a few usable materials. Streets such as Bombay St. and St. Gall’s Ave, would have instances of being sonically inactive or there would be enormous amounts of wind tampering any recorded audio.

As the summer approached, most of the areas began to receive an influx of tourists, as well residents were outside their homes due kids being finished with the school year and country holidays. This affected the placement of

the microphones to not interfere with local lifestyle and cultural tourism business. The unused ambisonics recordings to create Project 1 | Divided Spaces were then used for Project 2 | Peace Wall Belfast Soundwalk.

4.6 Extras: Stereo, binaural, contact, coil recordings

The other audio recordings were to either detail particular sounds from within the ambisonics files, or to highlight particular sonic activities and compositional materials to or from the Peace Wall area. These varied from physical touching of the cement, pushing on the metal sheets of the walls, recording natural sounds of the environment such as dogs or footsteps, and interpretive physical augmentation sonification with the contact microphone on a range of diverse surfaces.

The in-ear binaural microphone/earphones lacked quality and the harsh winds in the areas would damage the audio recordings. To create the binaural soundscapes, there was an increase of recording stereo and mono sources that would then use software to enhance the binaural experience.

5. PROJECT FORMATS

In the early stages of the research, there was a vision of using or extracting sounds from the Peace Wall and surrounding spaces with image/color sonification. However, as the year went on this idea shifted towards the compatibility with audio-geography or the ethnographic approach of the recordings. Inspired by Gallagher’s [14] research with his use of extensive ranges of microphones to heighten site specific interactions formed the building blocks for the final projects. The audio recordings gathered prompted diversity of material which led to amounts of transformation to create two distinctive projects. It is a combination of questioning, experiencing, and understanding these types of technologies to support the artistic practices in this research. [15]. These projects were not clearly conceptualized at the beginning of the research, instead, only through environmental experiences, technological learning, and continuous research did either of the projects form.

The final project formats are:

Project 1 | Divided Spaces – individual(s) experience being virtually placed between both sides of the Peace Wall Belfast and listen to experiences/stories of people affected. Initially created for the Sonic Lab at the Sonic Arts Research Centre, this project is also rendered for Binaural and Stereo experiences.

Project 2 | Peace Wall Belfast Soundwalk – walking a route around the Peace Wall Belfast and listening to six binaural soundscapes inspired by the spaces, materials, events, and community.

The projects connect by motivation and technology, to provide an opportunity to use spatial audio to share people’s relations to the ‘Troubles’ and in this context, the Peace Wall Belfast. Additionally, the conditions of each

project were to grant two opposite sonic experiences yet linked with research context. In one viewpoint, not having speech permitted to use in the Peace Wall Belfast Soundwalks forced critical creative decisions on how to manage representation without narration. On the other hand, having archival material and interviews for Divided Spaces required constraints on composition and duration to not simply produce an audio documentary, but an installation that could promote newer understandings

5.1 Divided Spaces

This research project focused on storytelling from interviews and BBC Northern Ireland archival material with the combination of various recording methods to create an audio immersive installation. In specific, it is to highlight the connectivity of spaces and experiences through sound to highlight past, present, and future relations with the Peace Wall Belfast. The foundation of the project rested on the spatial audio concept of ambisonics to have the piece distributed for different listening environments.

The research reflects on the experiences with Peace Walls and history of the ‘Troubles’, see Table 1, this undoubtedly provokes sensitivity towards sharing experiences and therefore was hard to obtain numerous participants. Consequently, this shaped the focus from the gathered interviews and archival material to maintain an anonymous and neutral viewpoint. This means that there are no names, occupations, religious, political, or background of an individual exposed throughout any of the audio. There is neither any personal intention to promote either community from the Falls or Shankill. It is the only project that includes voice from participants due to their consent to only have their experiences shared in private listening environments and cannot be used for the public work of Project 2 | Peace Wall Belfast Soundwalk.

Separated in sections to highlight the time period:

Section:	Time code:
Introduction	00:00 – 01:31
Past	01:32 – 06:17
Present	06:28 – 20:09
<i>Within Present – Peace Wall</i>	12:50 – 16:06
<i>Within Present – Sound Wall</i>	16:07 – 20:09
Future	20:10 – 22:13

Table 1. Timestamps of sections.

The project composition and workflow instilled new methods of using ambisonics audio for creating separated sonic fields, the entirety of the project was composed in Reaper and using SSA Plugins, see Figure 3. Ambisonics allows for the capturing of multiple sonic fields (360° audio) and with SSA Plugins (Decoder and Panner) provide an ability to achieve a new effect. By placing an SSA Panner on a 4 channel AmbiX audio track, then positioning the Azimuth either at 90° or -90° allows for directional listening of certain audio from the left and right sides. This

was combined as a layer to have directionality from certain audio characteristics identifying the Nationalist and Loyalist sides of the wall with unmodified 360° sound fields that would act as a general ambiance. This decoding and panning method led to an immersive space having capabilities of experiencing sonic division, as if the listener(s) took the position of the Peace Wall. Within the piece, sometimes the listener is exposed to either side of the wall, both of sides of the wall together, and even a mixture of separated/joined spaces.

Figure 2 - Workflow Diagram

Examples in Divided Spaces:

Listening:	Time code:
Either side of the wall	06:48 – 08:00 / 09:44 – 10:32
Both sides together	15:07 – 16:08
Mixture of separated/joined spaces	10:40 – 11:44

Table 2. Timestamps of examples.

Figure 3 - Listening Environment

Combining an array of audio material (ambisonics, stereo, mono sources), into a multi-layered and

segmental sonic field shifted the original concepts from an audio piece into an installation, see Figure 4. Using effects such as EQ and Reverb were either to shape sounds, harshness or noise, or to create sensations of feeling lost between both communities. The ability to take traditional concepts of ambisonics and use it in forms that can compress several large physical areas into an audio immersive installation assisted in the idea of simultaneously listening to both sides of the wall. The installation encourages for a listener(s) to walk through, around, and be virtually present between the two sides. It also supports the ability to embody the perceptions to and from the Peace Wall. This results in inspiring listener mobility to cross into either of the auditory spaces with their own free choice and therefore generates a unique sonic experience for that listener(s).

5.2 Peace Wall Belfast Soundwalks

This research project focused on having a flexible walking route with no fixed track list, to listen to six individualized binaural soundscapes inspired by local events, sonic activity, and creative perspectives of material interaction, see Figure 7 and Table 3. Each of the soundscapes vary in sound design and audio material to create an interleaved balance between the natural and perceptual sound environments. The listener(s) have complete freedom of going in either direction to listen to the soundscapes, or to listen to as many as they would like. This positions the listener(s) in the physical spaces of each soundscape and can try to connect material they hear from the piece to the surrounding areas.

Initially there was a desire to have locals recorded to highlight particular sonic interests of the areas and or details of any experiences, yet, all the participants did not agree to have their voice recorded for a public project that is accessed online. In terms of sonification there was an interest to perform image to sound sonification, however, the research from Weger, Hermann, and Höldrich [16] provided a new form of sonification from physical interaction of materials. The emphasis to focus on physical augmentation sonification, either with the contact or coil microphone, generated alternative perceptions of the materials which compose these spaces and shape the collectiveness of the Peace Wall. For instance, the peeling of the mural artwork creates a new listening experience when using a contact microphone and revealing that the artwork can produce sonic elements. As well, using a coil microphone to record electrical generators surrounding the Peace Wall which produce a range of frequencies indistinguishable by natural human hearing.

These unique forms of sonification were blended with natural recordings to establish a different viewpoint which are either overlooked, non-considered accessible, or visually unappealing. It seemed to establish an interesting model for the project's concept and message of how all these sounds interact within the spaces of the Peace Wall. Activating these ranges of materials produced interesting effects that were incorporated with the compositional structure and sound design of some of the soundscapes.

The six locations and main sonic activities are described below:

Street Location	Sonic Activity
St. Gall's Ave (bottom)	Community playground
St. Gall's Ave – Bombay St. (green field)	Interaction with nature and wall
Bombay St. – Kashmir Rd	Alternate perception of drummer and local community
Cupar Way – Lawnbrook Ave	Noise Pollution/ Drummer/ Tourist Congestion
Cupar Way (middle)	Material Interaction – Art-work Sonification
Cupar Way – Conway St.	Social events of The Twelfth (Orange Day)

Table 3. Description of locations.

These six binaural soundscapes entice a site-specific experience to discover new modes of engaging with the visual stature and presence of the Peace Walls. Audio documentation such as Cupar Way – Conway St. displays audio fragments of The Twelfth, a Protestant celebration, which is now available throughout the year when someone experiences the soundwalks. Whereas, Bombay St. – Kashmir Rd demonstrates perception of a sound produced from the opposite side of the wall, usually not a regular phenomenon.

To create these works, the soundscapes were composed from a range of ambiX (decoded to binaural), stereo, and mono sources and then using a binaural panner (Ambio Orbit) to create spatial movement. There are audio and effect modulation/editing to either enhance or reform certain sonic qualities. Each of the soundscapes have a duration of three minutes to allow time for reflection between locations and there is an equal number of soundscapes produced for both sides of the Peace Wall.

6. DEMONSTRATIONS

6.1 Divided Spaces in the Sonic Lab [22m13s]

The project demonstration used the Sonic Lab at the Sonic Arts Research Centre, an immersive listening laboratory with speakers located under, around, and on top of the audience. Visit <https://georgiosvaroutsos.com/divided-spaces/> to listen to a binaural render of the piece. [17].

Figure 4 - Divided Spaces | Video Screenshot

The Sonic Lab was visually divided by two lights, Green to indicate the Falls Road, and Orange/Red to indicate the Shankill Road. This was prepared to aid with the sonic complexities when representing either side and if certain points of speech were not comprehensible because

of the accent or audio quality. The space was cleared to freely walk around within the speaker arrangement and allow for possibilities of going on either side of the virtual Peace Wall. As an audio immersive installation in the Sonic Lab, the capabilities of utilizing the entire space acoustically and visually augmented the sonic experience.

The piece includes an anonymous narrator which guides the form and direction of the piece. The voice is placed at the front center arrangement for consistency throughout the installation. All the other voices take a “round-table” discussion within the virtual auditory space to allow hearing people's experiences or documentary material in a neutral setting. Throughout the piece there are moments of natural environment representation and amounts creative manipulation to enhance the immersive experience within the room. This meant applying reverb and delay effects to allow longevity of particular sounds or to imply a certain level of attention to a sound(s). The piece begins with the opening of a security gate and then ending with the security gates closing.

It is important to mention that due to certain legal constraints with BBC Northern Ireland; the project has permission to play (for the time being) only for the Sonic Lab at the Sonic Arts Research Centre. There are discussions to have permission to use the project for academic and artistic purposes.

6.2 Peace Wall Belfast Soundwalks at the Peace Wall Belfast [~1hr20mins]

Figure 5 - Soundwalk Participants

At the Peace Wall Belfast Soundwalks demonstration, participants were instructed to visit the material online: <https://georgiosvaroutsos.com/wallsounds/> and read the project information before beginning the walking route. [17].

As we approached the first location, they would look at the photos, read the instructional or informative text about the piece, and then listen to the audio file (repeated for each listening location). After each completed listening of the audio files, there were brief moments of discussions, and, personal sharing of knowledge about the experience or information that influenced the creation of the specific piece.

Having the experience from Project 1 | Divided Spaces, it seemed like that participants grew a deeper connection to the locations. Understanding how each of the compositions reflected one another based on the recorded stories and sonic characteristics of the spaces. They deliberately invoked themselves within the spaces, by observing, touching, and walking in their own free choice within the listening location. It is meant to inform the listener

about issues and relations that are unnoticed or time-specific in a mixture of natural and creative sound selections. My presence was at a minimal since the experience was for the participants to embrace and would allow for a clearer understanding on how the project affected them.

It is interesting to note that not all the participants followed one another within the perimeters of a listening location, there was a mixture of tailing one another and detaching from the group to listen in a different location within the specified area. Due to certain levels of ambiguity in the text, it is up to the listener to decide on how large the listening locations are to themselves. To produce a site-specific audio work of this nature is to increase engagement with locations that have a dominant effect on the Peace Wall Belfast or reveal parts of the community that are not always apparent from visual observations.

7. CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, the overall concept and motivation of this research project is aimed at introducing new artistic approaches to stimulate conversations of conflict transformations with the Peace Walls in Northern Ireland. This research investigated alternative approaches to question how audio augments perspectives and how can spatial audio technology impact the understanding of divided communities through two different listening experiences.

The outcome of projects is influenced by a year-long exploration and continuous capturing of field recordings to document sonic markers, community events, social interaction, and interviews. The addition of BBC Northern Ireland's archival material influenced the concepts messages of representing periods of history either not aware to the public and/or unattainable from any other sources. Without it, there would be a detachment to the ideas and voices of those affected from the beginning of the placing of the Peace Walls and how it continuously affects present day residents in Northern Ireland.

The only downside to the research was even with my outreach to community centers, tourist agencies, government bodies, and other agencies of conflict transformation, finding a larger number of willing participants to speak within the project was challenging. Additionally, there was the lack of knowledge of Northern Ireland religious holidays and festivities throughout the summer that affected finding people.

Finally, there was extensive effort to represent the stories and communities in an equally neutral perspective that combined socio-cultural elements to reflect the sounds and histories of these spaces. The discussion of participant experiences from the demonstrations revealed an embracing of new and refreshing point of views based on the tragic history of the 'Troubles' and construction of Peace Walls. Which continues to have an effect on segregating communities and the state of peace resolution in Northern Ireland. This research hopes to encourage future discussions on conflict resolution and using art as a platform for change.

8. REFERENCES

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